

EFFECT OF CFRP ON VORTEX-INDUCED VIBRATION OF A BRIMMED-DIFFUSER SHROUD FOR A WIND TURBINE

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1. Introduction

Brimmed-Diffuser Shroud (wind-lens)^[1]

Previous Work^[3]

Can CFRP reduce the VIV in the wind-lens?

- The use of the merits of CFRP
 - ✓ High-specific stiffness and strength
 - ✓ Anisotropic stiffness
 - ✓ Designed material properties
 - ✓ High damping capacity^[4]

2. Structural models

The original model

The CFRP models

- Three types for comparison
 - ✓ WL-D: CFRP Diffuser
 - ✓ WL-S: CFRP Support arms
 - ✓ WL-DS: CFRP Diffuser & Support arms
- CFRP diffuser
 - ✓ [0/60/-60]_{2s} with 0.2 mm plies
 - ✓ No ribs and corrugation
 - ✓ The same weight with WL-O*
 - ✓ Around 14 times the bending rigidity of WL-O
- CFRP support arm
 - ✓ Lengthwise unidirectional layup

*WL-O: The original model

3. Numerical Method

3D Modal analysis Finite Element Method

2D Aeroelastic analysis CFD program [5,6]

4. Results & Discussions

Mode shapes

- Five basic mode shapes

Aeroelastic Analysis

- Generalized coordinate & Displacement amplitude

- Rotational mode: MOST DOMINANT
 - ✓ Induced by the 2nd and 3rd vortex mode related to the drag force
- No effect of CFRP?
 - ➔ The reinforcement of the diffuser with CFRP makes the support arms relatively flexible.

Conclusion

To accomplish the effective structural reinforcement against the VIV, the balance of the rigidity of the diffuser and the support arms of the bending and torsional rigidity of the support arm needs to be considered!

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